

Positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideals of *BCK/BCI*-algebras

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ABSTRACT. The notion of positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal is introduced, and several properties are investigated. Relations between MBJ-neutrosophic ideal and positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal are discussed. Characterizations of positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal are displayed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In order to handle uncertainties in many real applications, the fuzzy set was introduced by L.A. Zadeh [19] in 1965. In 1983, K. Atanassov introduced the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy set as a generalization of fuzzy set. As a more general platform that extends the notions of classic set, (intuitionistic) fuzzy set and interval valued (intuitionistic) fuzzy set, the notion of neutrosophic set is initiated by Smarandache ([14], [15] and [16]). Neutrosophic algebraic structures in *BCK/BCI*-algebras are discussed in the papers [1], [2], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [12], [13], [17] and [18]. In [10], the notion of MBJ-neutrosophic sets is introduced as another generalization of neutrosophic set, it is applied to *BCK/BCI*-algebras. Mohseni et al. [10] introduced the concept of MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebras in *BCK/BCI*-algebras, and investigated related properties. They gave a characterization of MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra, and established a new MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra by using an MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra of a *BCI*-algebra. They considered the homomorphic inverse image of MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra, and discussed translation of MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra. Jun and Roh [11] applied the notion of MBJ-neutrosophic sets to ideals of *BCK/BI*-algebras, and introduce the concept of MBJ-neutrosophic ideals in *BCK/BCI*-algebras. They provided a condition for an

MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra to be an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal in a *BCK*-algebra, and considered conditions for an MBJ-neutrosophic set to be an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal in a *BCK/BCI*-algebra. They discussed relations between MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebras, MBJ-neutrosophic *o*-subalgebras and MBJ-neutrosophic ideals. In a *BCI*-algebra, they provided conditions for an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal to be an MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra, and considered a characterization of an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal in an (*S*)-*BCK*-algebra.

In this paper, we introduce the notion of positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal, and investigate several properties. We discuss relations between MBJ-neutrosophic ideal and positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal. We provide characterizations of positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal.

2. PRELIMINARIES

By a *BCI*-algebra, we mean a set X with a binary operation $*$ and a special element 0 that satisfies the following conditions:

- (I) $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$,
- (II) $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$,
- (III) $x * x = 0$,
- (IV) $x * y = 0, y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$,

for all $x, y, z \in X$. If a *BCI*-algebra X satisfies the following identity:

- (V) $(\forall x \in X) (0 * x = 0)$,

then X is called a *BCK*-algebra.

Every *BCK/BCI*-algebra X satisfies the following conditions:

- (2.1) $(\forall x \in X) (x * 0 = x)$,
- (2.2) $(\forall x, y, z \in X) (x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z, z * y \leq z * x)$,
- (2.3) $(\forall x, y, z \in X) ((x * y) * z = (x * z) * y)$,
- (2.4) $(\forall x, y, z \in X) ((x * z) * (y * z) \leq x * y)$

where $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

A nonempty subset S of a *BCK/BCI*-algebra X is called a subalgebra of X if $x * y \in S$, for all $x, y \in S$. A subset I of a *BCK/BCI*-algebra X is called an ideal of X , if it satisfies:

- (2.5) $0 \in I$,
- (2.6) $(\forall x \in X) (\forall y \in I) (x * y \in I \Rightarrow x \in I)$.

A subset I of a *BCK*-algebra X is called a positive implicative ideal of X (see [9]), if it satisfies (2.5) and

- (2.7) $(\forall x, y, z \in X) (((x * y) * z \in I, y * z \in I \Rightarrow x * z \in I)$.

By an interval number, we mean a closed subinterval $\tilde{a} = [a^-, a^+]$ of I , where $0 \leq a^- \leq a^+ \leq 1$. Denote by $[I]$ the set of all interval numbers. Let us define what is known as refined minimum (briefly, rmin) and refined maximum (briefly, rmax) of two elements in $[I]$. We also define the symbols “ \succeq ”, “ \preceq ”, “ $=$ ” in case of two

elements in $[I]$. Consider two interval numbers $\tilde{a}_1 := [a_1^-, a_1^+]$ and $\tilde{a}_2 := [a_2^-, a_2^+]$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{rmin} \{ \tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2 \} &= [\min \{ a_1^-, a_2^- \}, \min \{ a_1^+, a_2^+ \}], \\ \text{rmax} \{ \tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2 \} &= [\max \{ a_1^-, a_2^- \}, \max \{ a_1^+, a_2^+ \}], \\ \tilde{a}_1 \succeq \tilde{a}_2 &\Leftrightarrow a_1^- \geq a_2^-, a_1^+ \geq a_2^+, \end{aligned}$$

and similarly, we may have $\tilde{a}_1 \preceq \tilde{a}_2$ and $\tilde{a}_1 = \tilde{a}_2$. To say $\tilde{a}_1 \succ \tilde{a}_2$ (resp. $\tilde{a}_1 \prec \tilde{a}_2$), we mean $\tilde{a}_1 \succeq \tilde{a}_2$ and $\tilde{a}_1 \neq \tilde{a}_2$ (resp. $\tilde{a}_1 \preceq \tilde{a}_2$ and $\tilde{a}_1 \neq \tilde{a}_2$). Let $\tilde{a}_i \in [I]$, where $i \in \Lambda$. We define

$$\text{rinf}_{i \in \Lambda} \tilde{a}_i = \left[\inf_{i \in \Lambda} a_i^-, \inf_{i \in \Lambda} a_i^+ \right] \quad \text{and} \quad \text{rsup}_{i \in \Lambda} \tilde{a}_i = \left[\sup_{i \in \Lambda} a_i^-, \sup_{i \in \Lambda} a_i^+ \right].$$

Let X be a nonempty set. A function $A : X \rightarrow [I]$ is called an interval-valued fuzzy set (briefly, an IVF set) in X . Let $[I]^X$ stand for the set of all IVF sets in X . For every $A \in [I]^X$ and $x \in X$, $A(x) = [A^-(x), A^+(x)]$ is called the degree of membership of an element x to A , where $A^- : X \rightarrow I$ and $A^+ : X \rightarrow I$ are fuzzy sets in X which are called a lower fuzzy set and an upper fuzzy set in X , respectively. For simplicity, we denote $A = [A^-, A^+]$.

Let X be a non-empty set. A neutrosophic set (NS) in X (see [15]) is a structure of the form:

$$A := \{ \langle x; A_T(x), A_I(x), A_F(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$$

where $A_T : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a truth membership function, $A_I : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is an indeterminate membership function, and $A_F : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a false membership function.

We refer the reader to the books [3, 9] for further information regarding *BCK/BCI*-algebras, and to the site “<http://fs.gallup.unm.edu/neutrosophy.htm>” for further information regarding neutrosophic set theory.

Let X be a non-empty set. By an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X (see [10]), we mean a structure of the form:

$$\mathcal{A} := \{ \langle x; M_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(x), J_A(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \},$$

where M_A and J_A are fuzzy sets in X , which are called a truth membership function and a false membership function, respectively, and \tilde{B}_A is an IVF set in X which is called an indeterminate interval-valued membership function.

For the sake of simplicity, we shall use the symbol $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ for the MBJ-neutrosophic set

$$\mathcal{A} := \{ \langle x; M_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(x), J_A(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}.$$

Let X be a *BCK/BCI*-algebra. An MBJ-neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ in X is called an MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra of X (see [10]), if it satisfies:

$$(2.8) \quad (\forall x, y \in X) \left(\begin{array}{l} M_A(x * y) \geq \min \{ M_A(x), M_A(y) \}, \\ \tilde{B}_A(x * y) \succeq \text{rmin} \{ \tilde{B}_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(y) \}, \\ J_A(x * y) \leq \max \{ J_A(x), J_A(y) \}. \end{array} \right)$$

Let X be a BCK/BCI -algebra. An MBJ-neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ in X is called an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X (see [11]), if it satisfies:

$$(2.9) \quad (\forall x \in X) (M_A(0) \geq M_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(0) \succeq \tilde{B}_A(x), J_A(0) \leq J_A(x))$$

and

$$(2.10) \quad (\forall x, y \in X) \left(\begin{array}{l} M_A(x) \geq \min\{M_A(x * y), M_A(y)\} \\ \tilde{B}_A(x) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(x * y), \tilde{B}_A(y)\} \\ J_A(x) \leq \max\{J_A(x * y), J_A(y)\} \end{array} \right).$$

3. POSITIVE IMPLICATIVE MBJ-NEUTROSOPHIC IDEALS

In what follows, let X be a BCK -algebra unless otherwise specified.

Definition 3.1. An MBJ-neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ in X is called a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X , if it satisfies (2.9) and

$$(3.1) \quad (\forall x, y, z \in X) \left(\begin{array}{l} M_A(x * z) \geq \min\{M_A((x * y) * z), M_A(y * z)\} \\ \tilde{B}_A(x * z) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((x * y) * z), \tilde{B}_A(y * z)\} \\ J_A(x * z) \leq \max\{J_A((x * y) * z), J_A(y * z)\} \end{array} \right).$$

Example 3.2. Consider a BCK -algebra $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ with the binary operation $*$ which is given in Table 1:

TABLE 1. Cayley table for the binary operation “ $*$ ”

$*$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	0	2
3	3	3	3	0	3
4	4	4	4	4	0

Let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X defined by Table 2:

TABLE 2. MBJ-neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$

X	$M_A(x)$	$\tilde{B}_A(x)$	$J_A(x)$
0	0.7	[0.4, 0.9]	0.2
1	0.6	[0.3, 0.8]	0.5
2	0.5	[0.2, 0.6]	0.5
3	0.4	[0.1, 0.3]	0.7
4	0.3	[0.2, 0.5]	0.9

It is routine to verify that $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X .

Theorem 3.3. *Every positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal.*

Proof. If we take $z = 0$ in (3.1) and use (2.1), then we have the condition (2.10). Thus every positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal. \square

The converse of Theorem 3.3 is not true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.4. Consider a BCK-algebra $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ with the binary operation $*$ which is given in Table 3:

TABLE 3. Cayley table for the binary operation “ $*$ ”

$*$	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	a
b	b	a	0	b
c	c	c	c	0

Let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X defined by Table 4:

TABLE 4. MBJ-neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$

X	$M_A(x)$	$\tilde{B}_A(x)$	$J_A(x)$
0	0.7	[0.4, 0.9]	0.2
a	0.6	[0.3, 0.8]	0.6
b	0.6	[0.3, 0.8]	0.6
c	0.4	[0.1, 0.3]	0.4

It is routine to verify that $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . Since

$$M_A(b * a) = 0.6 < 0.7 = \min\{M_A((b * a) * a), M_A(a * a)\},$$

$\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is not a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X .

Lemma 3.5 ([11]). *Every MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X satisfies the following assertion.*

$$(3.2) \quad (\forall x, y \in X) \left(x \leq y \Rightarrow M_A(x) \geq M_A(y), \tilde{B}_A(x) \succeq \tilde{B}_A(y), J_A(x) \leq J_A(y) \right).$$

We provide conditions for an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal to be a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal.

Theorem 3.6. *An MBJ-neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ in X is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X if and only if it is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X satisfying the following condition.*

$$(3.3) \quad (\forall x, y \in X) \left(\begin{array}{l} M_A(x * y) \geq M_A((x * y) * y), \\ \tilde{B}_A(x * y) \succeq \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * y), \\ J_A(x * y) \leq J_A((x * y) * y). \end{array} \right)$$

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . If z is replaced by y in (3.1), then

$$\begin{aligned} M_A(x * y) &\geq \min\{M_A((x * y) * y), M_A(y * y)\} \\ &= \min\{M_A((x * y) * y), M_A(0)\} = M_A((x * y) * y), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}_A(x * y) &\succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((x * y) * y), \tilde{B}_A(y * y)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((x * y) * y), \tilde{B}_A(0)\} = \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * y), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} J_A(x * y) &\leq \max\{J_A((x * y) * y), J_A(y * y)\} \\ &= \max\{J_A((x * y) * y), J_A(0)\} = J_A((x * y) * y), \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y \in X$.

Conversely, let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X satisfying the condition (3.3). Since

$$((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * z) * y = (x * y) * z$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$, it follows from Lemma 3.5 that

$$(3.4) \quad \begin{array}{l} M_A((x * y) * z) \leq M_A(((x * z) * z) * (y * z)), \\ \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * z) \succeq \tilde{B}_A(((x * z) * z) * (y * z)), \\ J_A((x * y) * z) \geq J_A(((x * z) * z) * (y * z)), \end{array}$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$. Using (3.3), (2.10) and (3.4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} M_A(x * z) &\geq M_A((x * z) * z) \geq \min\{M_A(((x * z) * z) * (y * z)), M_A(y * z)\} \\ &\geq \min\{M_A((x * y) * z), M_A(y * z)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}_A(x * z) &\succeq \tilde{B}_A((x * z) * z) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(((x * z) * z) * (y * z)), \tilde{B}_A(y * z)\} \\ &\succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((x * y) * z), \tilde{B}_A(y * z)\}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} J_A(x * z) &\leq J_A((x * z) * z) \leq \max\{J_A(((x * z) * z) * (y * z)), J_A(y * z)\} \\ &\leq \max\{J_A((x * y) * z), J_A(y * z)\}, \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$. Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . \square

Theorem 3.7. Let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is positive implicative if and only if it satisfies the following condition.

$$(3.5) \quad (\forall x, y, z \in X) \left(\begin{array}{l} M_A((x * z) * (y * z)) \geq M_A((x * y) * z), \\ \tilde{B}_A((x * z) * (y * z)) \succeq \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * z), \\ J_A((x * z) * (y * z)) \leq J_A((x * y) * z). \end{array} \right)$$

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X by Theorem 3.3, and satisfies the condition (3.3) by Theorem 3.6. Since

$$((x * (y * z)) * z) * z = ((x * z) * (y * z)) * z \leq (x * y) * z,$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$, it follows from Lemma 3.5 that

$$(3.6) \quad \begin{array}{l} M_A((x * y) * z) \leq M_A(((x * (y * z)) * z) * z), \\ \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * z) \succeq \tilde{B}_A(((x * (y * z)) * z) * z), \\ J_A((x * y) * z) \geq J_A(((x * (y * z)) * z) * z), \end{array}$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$. Using (2.3), (3.3) and (3.6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} M_A((x * z) * (y * z)) &= M_A((x * (y * z)) * z) \\ &\geq M_A(((x * (y * z)) * z) * z) \\ &\geq M_A((x * y) * z), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}_A((x * z) * (y * z)) &= \tilde{B}_A((x * (y * z)) * z) \\ &\succeq \tilde{B}_A(((x * (y * z)) * z) * z) \\ &\succeq \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * z), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} J_A((x * z) * (y * z)) &= J_A((x * (y * z)) * z) \\ &\leq J_A(((x * (y * z)) * z) * z) \\ &\leq J_A((x * y) * z). \end{aligned}$$

Hence (3.5) is valid.

Conversely, let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X which satisfies the condition (3.5). If we put $z = y$ in (3.5) and use (III) and (2.1), then we obtain the condition (3.3). Thus $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X by Theorem 3.6. \square

Theorem 3.8. Let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X . Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X if and only if it satisfies the condition (2.9) and

$$(3.7) \quad (\forall x, y, z \in X) \left(\begin{array}{l} M_A(x * y) \geq \min\{M_A(((x * y) * y) * z), M_A(z)\}, \\ \tilde{B}_A(x * y) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(((x * y) * y) * z), \tilde{B}_A(z)\}, \\ J_A(x * y) \leq \max\{J_A(((x * y) * y) * z), J_A(z)\}. \end{array} \right)$$

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X (see Theorem 3.3), and so the condition (2.9) is valid. Using (2.10), (III), (2.1), (2.3) and (3.5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} M_A(x * y) &\geq \min\{M_A((x * y) * z), M_A(z)\} \\ &= \min\{M_A(((x * z) * y) * (y * y)), M_A(z)\} \\ &\geq \min\{M_A(((x * z) * y) * y), M_A(z)\} \\ &= \min\{M_A(((x * y) * y) * z), M_A(z)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}_A(x * y) &\succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((x * y) * z), \tilde{B}_A(z)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(((x * z) * y) * (y * y)), \tilde{B}_A(z)\} \\ &\succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(((x * z) * y) * y), \tilde{B}_A(z)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(((x * y) * y) * z), \tilde{B}_A(z)\}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} J_A(x * y) &\leq \max\{J_A((x * y) * z), J_A(z)\} \\ &= \max\{J_A(((x * z) * y) * (y * y)), J_A(z)\} \\ &\leq \max\{J_A(((x * z) * y) * y), J_A(z)\} \\ &= \max\{J_A(((x * y) * y) * z), J_A(z)\}, \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Conversely, let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X which satisfies conditions (2.9) and (3.7). Then

$$\begin{aligned} M_A(x) &= M_A(x * 0) \geq \min\{M_A(((x * 0) * 0) * z), M_A(z)\} \\ &= \min\{M_A(x * z), M_A(z)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}_A(x) &= \tilde{B}_A(x * 0) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(((x * 0) * 0) * z), \tilde{B}_A(z)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(x * z), \tilde{B}_A(z)\}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} J_A(x) &= J_A(x * 0) \leq \max\{J_A(((x * 0) * 0) * z), J_A(z)\} \\ &= \max\{J_A(x * z), J_A(z)\}, \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, z \in X$. Thus $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . Taking $z = 0$ in (3.7) and using (2.1) and (2.9) imply that

$$\begin{aligned} M_A(x * y) &\geq \min\{M_A(((x * y) * y) * 0), M_A(0)\} \\ &= \min\{M_A((x * y) * y), M_A(0)\} \\ &= M_A((x * y) * y), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{B}_A(x * y) &\succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(((x * y) * y) * 0), \tilde{B}_A(0)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((x * y) * y), \tilde{B}_A(0)\} \\ &= \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * y),\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}J_A(x * y) &\leq \max\{J_A(((x * y) * y) * 0), J_A(0)\} \\ &= \max\{J_A((x * y) * y), J_A(0)\} \\ &= J_A((x * y) * y),\end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y \in X$. It follows from Theorem 3.6 that $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . \square

Lemma 3.9 ([11]). *Let X be a BCK/BCI-algebra. Then every MBJ-neutrosophic ideal $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ of X satisfies the following assertion.*

$$(3.8) \quad x * y \leq z \Rightarrow \begin{cases} M_A(x) \geq \min\{M_A(y), M_A(z)\}, \\ \tilde{B}_A(x) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(y), \tilde{B}_A(z)\}, \\ J_A(x) \leq \max\{J_A(y), J_A(z)\}, \end{cases}$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Lemma 3.10. *If an MBJ-neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ in X satisfies the condition (3.8), then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X .*

Proof. Since $0 * x \leq x$ and $x * (x * y) \leq y$ for all $x, y \in X$, it follows from (3.8) that

$$M_A(0) \geq M_A(x), \tilde{B}_A(0) \succeq \tilde{B}_A(x), J_A(0) \leq J_A(x)$$

and $M_A(x) \geq \min\{M_A(x * y), M_A(y)\}$, $\tilde{B}_A(x) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(x * y), \tilde{B}_A(y)\}$ and

$$J_A(x) \leq \max\{J_A(x * y), J_A(y)\}.$$

Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . \square

Theorem 3.11. *Let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X . Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X if and only if it satisfies the following condition.*

$$(3.9) \quad (((x * y) * y) * a) * b = 0 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} M_A(x * y) \geq \min\{M_A(a), M_A(b)\}, \\ \tilde{B}_A(x * y) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(a), \tilde{B}_A(b)\}, \\ J_A(x * y) \leq \max\{J_A(a), J_A(b)\}, \end{cases}$$

for all $x, y, a, b \in X$.

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X (see Theorem 3.3). Let $a, b, x, y \in X$ be such that $(((x * y) * y) * a) * b = 0$. Then

$$M_A(x * y) \geq M_A((x * y) * y) \geq \min\{M_A(a), M_A(b)\},$$

$$\tilde{B}_A(x * y) \succeq \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * y) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(a), \tilde{B}_A(b)\},$$

and $J_A(x * y) \leq J_A((x * y) * y) \leq \max\{J_A(a), J_A(b)\}$ by Theorem 3.6 and Lemma 3.9. Thus (3.9) is valid.

Conversely, let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X which satisfies the condition (3.9). Let $x, a, b \in X$ be such that $x * a \leq b$. Then

$$(((x * 0) * 0) * a) * b = 0,$$

and so

$$M_A(x) = M_A(x * 0) \geq \min\{M_A(a), M_A(b)\},$$

$$\tilde{B}_A(x) = \tilde{B}_A(x * 0) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(a), \tilde{B}_A(b)\},$$

and

$$J_A(x) = J_A(x * 0) \leq \max\{J_A(a), J_A(b)\}$$

by (2.1) and (3.9). Thus $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X by Lemma 3.10. Since $(((x * y) * y) * ((x * y) * y)) * 0 = 0$ for all $x, y \in X$, we have

$$M_A(x * y) \geq \min\{M_A((x * y) * y), M_A(0)\} = M_A((x * y) * y),$$

$$\tilde{B}_A(x * y) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((x * y) * y), \tilde{B}_A(0)\} = \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * y),$$

and

$$J_A(x * y) \leq \max\{J_A((x * y) * y), J_A(0)\} = J_A((x * y) * y)$$

by (3.9). It follows from Theorem 3.6 that $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . \square

Theorem 3.12. *Let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X . Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X if and only if it satisfies the following condition.*

$$(3.10) \quad \begin{aligned} M_A((x * z) * (y * z)) &\geq \min\{M_A(a), M_A(b)\}, \\ \tilde{B}_A((x * z) * (y * z)) &\succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(a), \tilde{B}_A(b)\}, \\ J_A((x * z) * (y * z)) &\leq \max\{J_A(a), J_A(b)\}, \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y, z, a, b \in X$ with $((x * y) * z) * a * b = 0$.

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is an MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X (see Theorem 3.3). Let $a, b, x, y, z \in X$ be such that $((x * y) * z) * a * b = 0$. Using Theorem 3.7 and Lemma 3.9, we have

$$M_A((x * z) * (y * z)) \geq M_A((x * y) * z) \geq \min\{M_A(a), M_A(b)\},$$

$$\tilde{B}_A((x * z) * (y * z)) \succeq \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * z) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(a), \tilde{B}_A(b)\},$$

and

$$J_A((x * z) * (y * z)) \leq J_A((x * y) * z) \leq \max\{J_A(a), J_A(b)\}.$$

Conversely, let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X which satisfies the condition (3.10). Let $x, y, a, b \in X$ be such that $((x * y) * y) * a * b = 0$. Then

$$M_A(x * y) = M_A((x * y) * (y * y)) \geq \min\{M_A(a), M_A(b)\},$$

$$\tilde{B}_A(x * y) = \tilde{B}_A((x * y) * (y * y)) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(a), \tilde{B}_A(b)\},$$

and

$$J_A(x * y) = J_A((x * y) * (y * y)) \leq \max\{J_A(a), J_A(b)\}$$

by (2.1), (III) and (3.10). It follows from Theorem 3.11 that $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . \square

Theorem 3.13. *Let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X . Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X if and only if it satisfies the following condition.*

$$(3.11) \quad \begin{aligned} M_A(x * y) &\geq \min\{M_A(a_1), M_A(a_2), \dots, M_A(a_n)\}, \\ \tilde{B}_A(x * y) &\succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(a_1), \tilde{B}_A(a_2), \dots, \tilde{B}_A(a_n)\}, \\ J_A(x * y) &\leq \max\{J_A(a_1), J_A(a_2), \dots, J_A(a_n)\}, \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in X$ with $(\dots(((x * y) * y) * a_1) * \dots) * a_n = 0$.

Proof. It is similar to the proof of Theorem 3.11. \square

Theorem 3.14. *Let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be an MBJ-neutrosophic set in X . Then $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X if and only if it satisfies the following condition.*

$$(3.12) \quad \begin{aligned} M_A((x * z) * (y * z)) &\geq \min\{M_A(a_1), M_A(a_2), \dots, M_A(a_n)\}, \\ \tilde{B}_A((x * z) * (y * z)) &\succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A(a_1), \tilde{B}_A(a_2), \dots, \tilde{B}_A(a_n)\}, \\ J_A((x * z) * (y * z)) &\leq \max\{J_A(a_1), J_A(a_2), \dots, J_A(a_n)\}, \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y, z, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in X$ with $(\dots(((x * y) * z) * a_1) * \dots) * a_n = 0$.

Proof. It is similar to the proof of Theorem 3.12. \square

Given an MBJ-neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ in X , we consider the following sets.

$$\begin{aligned} U(M_A; \alpha) &:= \{x \in X \mid M_A(x) \geq \alpha\}, \\ U(\tilde{B}_A; [\delta_1, \delta_2]) &:= \{x \in X \mid \tilde{B}_A(x) \succeq [\delta_1, \delta_2]\}, \\ L(J_A; \beta) &:= \{x \in X \mid J_A(x) \leq \beta\}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ and $[\delta_1, \delta_2] \in [I]$.

Theorem 3.15. *An MBJ-neutrosophic set $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ in X is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X if and only if the non-empty sets $U(M_A; \alpha)$, $U(\tilde{B}_A; [\delta_1, \delta_2])$ and $L(J_A; \beta)$ are positive implicative ideals of X , for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ and $[\delta_1, \delta_2] \in [I]$.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ be a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . Let $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ and $[\delta_1, \delta_2] \in [I]$ be such that $U(M_A; \alpha)$, $U(\tilde{B}_A; [\delta_1, \delta_2])$ and $L(J_A; \beta)$ are non-empty. Obviously, $0 \in U(M_A; \alpha) \cap U(\tilde{B}_A; [\delta_1, \delta_2]) \cap L(J_A; \beta)$. For any $x, y, z, a, b, c, u, v, w \in X$, if $(x * y) * z \in U(M_A; \alpha)$, $y * z \in U(M_A; \alpha)$,

$(a * b) * c \in U(\tilde{B}_A; [\delta_1, \delta_2])$, $b * c \in U(\tilde{B}_A; [\delta_1, \delta_2])$, $(u * v) * w \in L(J_A; \beta)$ and $v * w \in L(J_A; \beta)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} M_A(x * z) &\geq \min\{M_A((x * y) * z), M_A(y * z)\} \geq \min\{\alpha, \alpha\} = \alpha, \\ \tilde{B}_A(a * c) &\succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((a * b) * c), \tilde{B}_A(b * c)\} \succeq \text{rmin}\{[\delta_1, \delta_2], [\delta_1, \delta_2]\} = [\delta_1, \delta_2], \\ J_A(u * w) &\leq \max\{J_A((u * v) * w), J_A(v * w)\} \leq \min\{\beta, \beta\} = \beta, \end{aligned}$$

and so $x * z \in U(M_A; \alpha)$, $a * c \in U(\tilde{B}_A; [\delta_1, \delta_2])$ and $u * w \in L(J_A; \beta)$. Therefore $U(M_A; \alpha)$, $U(\tilde{B}_A; [\delta_1, \delta_2])$ and $L(J_A; \beta)$ are positive implicative ideals of X .

Conversely, assume that the non-empty sets $U(M_A; \alpha)$, $U(\tilde{B}_A; [\delta_1, \delta_2])$ and $L(J_A; \beta)$ are positive implicative ideals of X for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ and $[\delta_1, \delta_2] \in [I]$. Assume that $M_A(0) < M_A(a)$, $\tilde{B}_A(0) \prec \tilde{B}_A(a)$ and $J_A(0) > J_A(a)$, for some $a \in X$. Then $0 \notin U(M_A; M_A(a)) \cap U(\tilde{B}_A; \tilde{B}_A(a)) \cap L(J_A; J_A(a))$, which is a contradiction. Thus $M_A(0) \geq M_A(x)$, $\tilde{B}_A(0) \succeq \tilde{B}_A(x)$ and $J_A(0) \leq J_A(x)$, for all $x \in X$. If

$$M_A(a_0 * c_0) < \min\{M_A((a_0 * b_0) * c_0), M_A(b_0 * c_0)\},$$

for some $a_0, b_0, c_0 \in X$, then $(a_0 * b_0) * c_0 \in U(M_A; t_0)$ and $b_0 * c_0 \in U(M_A; t_0)$ but $a_0 * c_0 \notin U(M_A; t_0)$ for $t_0 := \min\{M_A((a_0 * b_0) * c_0), M_A(b_0 * c_0)\}$. This is a contradiction, and thus

$$M_A(a * c) \geq \min\{M_A((a * b) * c), M_A(b * c)\},$$

for all $a, b, c \in X$.

Similarly, we can show that $J_A(a * c) \leq \max\{J_A((a * b) * c), J_A(b * c)\}$, for all $a, b, c \in X$. Suppose that $\tilde{B}_A(a_0 * c_0) \prec \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((a_0 * b_0) * c_0), \tilde{B}_A(b_0 * c_0)\}$, for some $a_0, b_0, c_0 \in X$. Let $\tilde{B}_A((a_0 * b_0) * c_0) = [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]$, $\tilde{B}_A(b_0 * c_0) = [\lambda_3, \lambda_4]$ and $\tilde{B}_A(a_0 * c_0) = [\delta_1, \delta_2]$. Then

$$[\delta_1, \delta_2] \prec \text{rmin}\{[\lambda_1, \lambda_2], [\lambda_3, \lambda_4]\} = [\min\{\lambda_1, \lambda_3\}, \min\{\lambda_2, \lambda_4\}],$$

and so $\delta_1 < \min\{\lambda_1, \lambda_3\}$ and $\delta_2 < \min\{\lambda_2, \lambda_4\}$. Taking

$$[\gamma_1, \gamma_2] := \frac{1}{2} \left(\tilde{B}_A(a_0 * c_0) + \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((a_0 * b_0) * c_0), \tilde{B}_A(b_0 * c_0)\} \right)$$

implies that

$$\begin{aligned} [\gamma_1, \gamma_2] &= \frac{1}{2} ([\delta_1, \delta_2] + [\min\{\lambda_1, \lambda_3\}, \min\{\lambda_2, \lambda_4\}]) \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{2}(\delta_1 + \min\{\lambda_1, \lambda_3\}), \frac{1}{2}(\delta_2 + \min\{\lambda_2, \lambda_4\}) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\min\{\lambda_1, \lambda_3\} > \gamma_1 = \frac{1}{2}(\delta_1 + \min\{\lambda_1, \lambda_3\}) > \delta_1$$

and

$$\min\{\lambda_2, \lambda_4\} > \gamma_2 = \frac{1}{2}(\delta_2 + \min\{\lambda_2, \lambda_4\}) > \delta_2.$$

Thus $[\min\{\lambda_1, \lambda_3\}, \min\{\lambda_2, \lambda_4\}] \succ [\gamma_1, \gamma_2] \succ [\delta_1, \delta_2] = \tilde{B}_A(a_0 * c_0)$. So

$$a_0 * c_0 \notin U(\tilde{B}_A; [\gamma_1, \gamma_2]).$$

On the other hand,

$$\tilde{B}_A((a_0 * b_0) * c_0) = [\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \succeq [\min\{\lambda_1, \lambda_3\}, \min\{\lambda_2, \lambda_4\}] \succ [\gamma_1, \gamma_2]$$

and

$$\tilde{B}_A(b_0 * c_0) = [\lambda_3, \lambda_4] \succeq [\min\{\lambda_1, \lambda_3\}, \min\{\lambda_2, \lambda_4\}] \succ [\gamma_1, \gamma_2],$$

that is, $(a_0 * b_0) * c_0, b_0 * c_0 \in U(\tilde{B}_A; [\gamma_1, \gamma_2])$. This is a contradiction. Hence

$$\tilde{B}_A(x * z) \succeq \text{rmin}\{\tilde{B}_A((x * y) * z), \tilde{B}_A(y * z)\},$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$. Consequently, $\mathcal{A} = (M_A, \tilde{B}_A, J_A)$ is a positive implicative MBJ-neutrosophic ideal of X . \square

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